

ISic0096

I.Sicily inscription 0096

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico
Baldassare Romano, inventory 121

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line

1
: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to

2
: mm

Text

1. [Cn(aeo)P]ollieno
2. [t]r(ibuno) · mil(itum)
3. [c(ives) r(omani) et A]thenienses

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285278

EDR 127499
EDCS 22100051

Bibliography

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